

Tapis User Interface for Machine learning Edge

Edge

- Computing power
- Memory
- Battery
- Storage

Images are transferred
to the datacenter

Data Center

- Network bandwidth to send data to center
- Delay of data analysis

User

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Users can initialize a new analysis by,

1. Selection existing ML models (like MegaDetector)
2. Choosing a dataset available/upload their own
3. Choose the hardware in which they want to execute
4. Add advanced configuration, if any

UUID	Analysis ID	Date	Status	Site	Model	Dataset	Report
uuid	Analysis1	7/29/2024, 5:30:00 PM	Done	TACC	megadetector5-ft-ena	Ohio Small Animals dataset	Download
uuid	Analysis2	7/29/2024, 5:30:00 PM	Done	CHAMELEON	megadetector5b	ENA dataset	Download
uuid	Analysis3	7/29/2024, 5:30:00 PM	Done	TACC	megadetector5a	ENA dataset	Download
uuid	Analysis4	7/29/2024, 5:30:00 PM	Done	CHAMELEON	megadetector5a	Ohio Small Animals dataset	Download

Creates Job request

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Deploy ML models
on the Edge device

Model Optimization

Resource utilization

- Memory
- Storage
- Power consumption
- Bandwidth

